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ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific coordination, project management and sustainability

D8.8 Reports from Advisory Board and Ethic Report 1

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Abstract

The Advisory Board (AB) in ConcePTION is the independent consultant body for the management of the consortium. During the proposal stage, ConcePTION aimed to install a diverse AB specialised in relevant scientific and ethical fields. This was successfully completed in 2020, sometime after the first year of the project.

The AB will not have decision authority in the project but will provide advice and feedback on the activities and results of ConcePTION. The AB will advise on project strategies for global impact, help solve major project risks with pragmatic advice, and provide input on sustainability, including global adoption of methods that are developed in ConcePTION. They will also be invited to the General Assembly Meeting as well as to annual meetings that will be held between the AB and the Managing Board. This deliverable, the first in the series of five, titled Reports from Advisory Board and Ethic Report 1 will only focus on who the AB members are and provide information about their background, their expertise etc., as this was the primary focus in the first year. The subsequent reports will cover more about the AB's annual feedback, comments and suggestions starting from year 2.

Key Attributes

The selection of the AB members was based on the following key attributes:

1. **Experienced:** A track record of significant scientific achievement and leadership, and Ethics research field.
2. **Strategic:** Can provide an objective and unique perspective on areas ConcePTION covers to maximize global outreach
3. **Influential:** Can advise on policy-related areas, understanding local and global perspectives to drive adoption of innovative approaches
4. **Connectivity:** Can suggest alliances with other researchers to help build synergies
5. **Thinks holistically to address the needs of women and their families:** can advise in the context of multiple stakeholders' concerns, while keeping patient needs at the forefront
6. **Builds future global capability and sustainability:** Represents viewpoints of a major geographical region, e.g., US, and if possible, Asia & Africa, a major agency (e.g., health authority), sector needed to build future capability (e.g., big data), etc. Because of the EU based funding, we should ensure that at least half of the SAB is from Europe.
7. **Advocates:** Can raise the profile and awareness of the project with relevant leaders in the scientific and policy arenas

Members of the Advisory Board

Sabine Straus (EU)

At its July 2018 meeting, the European Medicines Agency's (EMA) Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC) elected Sabine Straus from the Netherlands as its new Chair, for a three-year mandate starting in September 2018. She will replace June Raine, Director of Vigilance

and Risk Management of Medicines at the United Kingdom's Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory agency (MHRA), who will retire as Chair in September 2018, having served the maximum of two 3-year mandates.

Lynne Yao (US)

Lynne Yao, MD, is a Medical Officer Team Leader in the Division of Gastroenterology and Inborn Errors Products, Center for Drug Evaluation and Research, US Food and Drug Administration. The Inborn Errors of Metabolism Team is a review team that focuses on products for rare, inherited metabolic diseases including many biological products used as enzyme replacement therapies for these disorders. Dr. Yao is board certified in Pediatrics and Pediatric Nephrology. She joined the FDA in February 2008, and prior to this she was the Co-Medical Director at the Inova Pediatric Kidney Center, Inova Fairfax Hospital for Children in Fairfax, VA. She served as an officer in the US Army Medical Corps from 1989 to 2000 and was the Chief of Pediatric Nephrology Service at Walter Reed Army Medical Center from 1996 to 2000. She received her medical degree at the George Washington University School of Medicine, completed her training in Pediatrics at Walter Reed Army Medical Center, and her fellowship training in Pediatric Nephrology at Georgetown University Children's Medical Center.

Niklas Norén (EU)

Niklas Norén, PhD, is Chief Science Officer and Head of Research at the Uppsala Monitoring Centre. He is responsible for the scientific direction of the center and oversees 25 pharmacists, data scientists and medical doctors engaged in scientific development, safety signal detection and capacity building. He has published extensively on statistical pattern discovery in observational medical data, primarily adverse event reports and electronic medical records. His research on duplicate detection and subgroup discovery has been internationally awarded. In Europe, he has led collaborative projects in pharmacovigilance funded by the European Commission including: the signal detection work-package in PROTECT; the work-packages on detecting substandard medicines and drug dependence from adverse event reports in Monitoring Medicines; and the social media analytics work-package in WEB-RADR. Internationally, he led Uppsala Monitoring Centre's contributions to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership and is a member of the editorial board for Drug Safety. He is currently engaged in the IMI EHDEN project, in the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) collaborative and in a study of signal detection within the Sentinel Initiative. Dr. Norén holds a PhD in Mathematical Statistics from Stockholm University in 2007 and a Master's degree in Engineering Physics from Chalmers University of Technology in 2002. He has worked in various positions at the Uppsala Monitoring Centre and affiliated organizations since 2003.

Matthews Mathai (EU)

Dr Matthews Mathai is the Coordinator of the Epidemiology, Monitoring and Evaluation Team in WHO's Department of Maternal, Newborn, Child and Adolescent Health. In his former position at WHO, he worked in Making Pregnancy Safer contributing to the development, update and implementation of WHO's Integrated Management of Pregnancy and Childbirth (IMPAC) guidelines. Before joining WHO, Dr Mathai was Professor of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Christian Medical College, Vellore, India until 2005. He has also worked in many countries in Asia and the Pacific, training health workers in reproductive health, particularly in maternal and perinatal care. He established and directed the Regional Training and Research Centre in Reproductive Health at the

Fiji School of Medicine, Suva, Fiji (1996-97). Dr Mathai did his medical studies and postgraduate training in obstetrics and gynaecology at the Christian Medical College, Vellore, followed by further training at the University of Liverpool in feto-maternal medicine. He was awarded PhD in International Health by the Karolinska Institute, Stockholm. Dr Mathai has authored or co-authored over 100 scientific articles and book chapters.

Elizabeth Conover (US)

Beth is a nurse practitioner and certified genetic counselor within the Munroe-Meyer Institute's Department of Genetic medicine at the University of Nebraska Medical Center where she specializes in the diagnosis, management, and treatment of genetic conditions. A genetics consultation with Beth may include discussion of family history and recommendation and coordination of diagnostic and/or laboratory testing which can provide families and primary care providers with information necessary to ensure proper medical management of an affected individual. Additionally, genetic risks may be communicated to families when appropriate. General and specialized clinics are available, and appointments are scheduled within the clinic most appropriate for a patient's reason for referral

Christina Chambers (US)

Dr. Chambers is a professor of pediatrics at University of California, San Diego and Director of Clinical Research for the Department of Pediatrics at UCSD and Rady Children's Hospital. She is a perinatal epidemiologist, whose research is focused on environmental exposures and pregnancy and child health outcomes, including birth defects. She co-directs the Center for the Promotion of Maternal Health and Infant Development in the Department of Pediatrics at UCSD and is the Program Director of MotherToBabyCalifornia - a telephone-based service providing individualized risk assessments for pregnant women and their providers in the State of California. She is a founding principal investigator for the Vaccines and Medications in Pregnancy Surveillance System (VAMPSS) which is the first national system to evaluate medication and vaccine safety in human pregnancy, currently funded by the US DHHS, CDC, FDA and the National Vaccine Program Office. She headed the National Children's Study San Diego site, and has conducted

Robert Califf (US)

Robert Califf, MD MACC, is the Donald F. Fortin, MD, Professor of Cardiology. He is also Professor of Medicine in the Division of Cardiology and remains a practicing cardiologist. Dr. Califf was the Commissioner of Food and Drugs in 2016-2017 and Deputy Commissioner for Medical Products and Tobacco from February 2015 until his appointment as Commissioner in February 2016. Prior to joining the FDA, Dr. Califf was a professor of medicine and vice chancellor for clinical and translational research at Duke University. He also served as director of the Duke Translational Medicine Institute and founding director of the Duke Clinical Research Institute. He was the founding director of the Duke Clinical Research Institute, which is considered "the world's largest academic research organization" with 1000 employees and an annual budget of \$320 million, 50-60% of which is funded from industry. A nationally and internationally recognized expert in cardiovascular medicine, health outcomes research, healthcare quality, and clinical research, Dr. Califf has led many landmark clinical trials and is one of the most frequently cited authors in biomedical science, with more than 1,200 publications in the peer-reviewed literature
Ethics AB

Nikolaus Forgo (Austria)

Extensive dogmatic and third-party funded research for European, German and Austrian clients regarding questions on IT law, in particular data protection and data security law. Evaluation and consulting activities i.e. for the European Commission, the German Research Foundation, the German Ethics Council as well as various German and Austrian ministries.

Elselijn Kingma (UK)

Associate Professor in Philosophy at the University of Southampton. Between completing her PhD in Cambridge in 2008 and joining Southampton in 2013, Elselijn held positions at the National Institutes of Health, Bethesda (USA); King's College London, and Cambridge. Elselijn's has research interests in philosophy of medicine, philosophy of biology, metaphysics and applied ethics. From 2016 she is Principal Investigator on a five year, 1.2 million Euro ERC Starting Grant entitled 'Better Understanding the Metaphysics of Pregnancy'. Elselijn also has a part-time appointment as Socrates Professor in Philosophy and Technology in the Humanist Tradition, at the University of Eindhoven (NL). Before studying Philosophy, Elselijn obtained undergraduate degrees in Clinical Medicine (2004) and Cognitive & Neuro Psychology (2004) at the University of Leiden, the Netherlands.

Jan Piasecki (EU)

Jan Piasecki is an assistant professor at Jagiellonian University Medical College. He holds a doctorate degree in philosophy (Jagiellonian University, 2010) and Erasmus Mundus Master of Bioethics (2010-2011). He also studied philosophy at the Tilburg University in the Netherlands (Socrates/Erasmus 2005) and at International Academy of Philosophy in Santiago de Chile (2006). In May 2016, he was a visiting scholar of Erasmus Mundus Master of Bioethics at the University of Padova. He is a principal investigator in the project: Ethical Principles for Learning Health Care System funded by National Science Centre (Sonata 10, UMO-2015/19/D/HS1/00991).